

DETERMINATION OF FLAVONOIDS UZING THE METHOD OF EXTRACTION FROM THE HERNIARIA GLABRA PLANT

Makhmudkhonova N.S.

*Sanoyev A.I.

Chulpanov K.A.*

*The Tashkent Pharmaceutical institute

UZB F.A. S.Yu. Yunusov Institute for Plant Substance Chemistry

e-mail: sanoev.a85@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12670515>

Relevance: Currently, more than 40% of the medicines used in medical practice are natural products derived from plant raw materials. Due to the increasing demand for natural products, the demand for biologically active substances derived from plant materials is increasing from year to year. One of the most widely distributed plants within the territory of Uzbekistan is the *Herniaria glabra*, which is also one of the least-studied plants when it comes to its composition and biological activity. According to literature, this plant accumulates large amounts of triterpene saponins on its surface, and these are widely used as a diuretic in medicine for conditions such as heart disease, kidney disease, rheumatism, and arthritis. [1].

The purpose of this research: Optimal conditions for the extraction of triterpene saponins from the above-ground parts of the *Herniaria glabra* plant collected in the Ferghana Valley were investigated. The type of extraction, the degree of grinding of the raw materials, the choice of solvent, the time and duration of extraction, as well as drying conditions for the resulting extracts, were all studied.

Materials and Styles: The above-ground parts of the *Herniaria glabra* plant were used to various degrees of fineness. Extraction methods such as percolation, which involves the use of ultrasound and aqueous solutions of ethyl alcohol and methanol, were used. All materials, tools, and equipment necessary for the process were used.

Results: The above-ground parts of the *herniaria glabra* plant were extracted using percolation at room temperature with an aqueous solution of ethyl alcohol at various concentrations, as well as with methanol. Optimal extraction was achieved by using an aqueous solution containing 70% ethyl alcohol and finely ground, vegetable raw materials that were sized between 2 and 3 millimeters. The extraction process was done 5 times over a period of 30 hours, resulting in the extraction of 15.2% triterpene-rich saponin extractives. In order to minimize the time required for extraction and maximize the yield of the extract, an ultrasonic method was employed. For this purpose, hydraulic module ratios between 1 and 12 were used, as well as extraction times of 30 minutes, 15 minutes, and 15 seconds. The resulting extracts were then filtered and concentrated into an aqueous form using a rotary evaporator, while maintaining temperatures below 60 degrees Celsius. The dark extract was then dried in a vacuum drying chamber at 60 degrees Celsius for two hours. After drying, the dried extract was ground, and its amount was determined to be 18.5% relative to the mass of the original starting material. According to studies, saponins can comprise up to 1-5% of the plant material they are extracted from. From 50 grams of dry plant material, an average of 3% was obtained:

$50 * 3\% = 1.5$ grams

Chromatographically, 1,405 grams of the resulting material was obtained.

$$(1.5 - 1.405) / 1.5 * 100\% = 0.533\%$$

In addition to obtaining saponins, the above-mentioned process was also used to obtain flavonoids. In this study, 2.5 grams of flavonoids were extracted from 250 milliliters of the extract, and it was found that the extract contained 1% flavonoids on average.

Conclusions : When extracting the above-ground part of the *Herniaria glabra* plant using two different methods, it was determined that the advantage of using ultrasonic extraction characterized by a shorter extraction time and a higher content of extracts is optimal. Currently, scientific research is continuing on the physicochemical analysis of the resulting dry extract as well as the isolation of pure forms of substances containing triterpene saponins.

Used literature:

1. И. А. Губанов, К. В. Киселёва, В. С. Новиков, В. Н. Тихомиров /*Herniaria glabra* L. — Грыжник голый // Иллюстрированный определитель растений Средней России:.